

RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF MEDICAL RECORDS OF PATIENTS WITH UROLITHIASIS**Eshmurodova F.***basic doctoral student of the department Department of pharmaceutical organization of the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute*

ORCID:0009-0005-2703-2867

Suyunov N.*Doctor of Sciences in Pharmaceutics, professor, Head of Department of pharmaceutical organization of the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute*

ORCID: 0000-0002-2712-958X

Abstract

A retrospective study was conducted on the basis of medical records of 1,839 patients with urolithiasis. The study analyzed the incidence of urolithiasis, risk factors for recurrence, surgical procedures, and medications used to treat the disease. The results showed that urolithiasis occurs mainly in men of working age, and in women, the pharmaco-economic frequency of drug use in the disease is higher. More than 75% of patients had comorbidities such as dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and metabolic syndrome. The most frequently performed surgical methods were percutaneous nephrolithotomy and retrograde intrarenal surgery, and the drugs sodium chloride solution, diclofenac sodium, furosemide, ceftazidime, and extrema were used with the highest pharmaco-economic frequency in clinical practice, and the costs were higher for these drugs. It was found that their dosage form, dosage, and frequency of use were related to the severity of the disease.

Keywords: urolithiasis, urolithiasis, retrospective analysis, nephrolithotomy, lithotripsy, antibiotic therapy, drugs, patients.

Relevance. In the world, the following studies have been conducted on urolithiasis and its treatment, including retrospective and pharmaco-economic frequency analyses. In particular, urolithiasis is a metabolic disease that, under the influence of endogenous and exogenous factors, leads to the formation of stones in the urinary tract due to an imbalance in the physico-chemical balance of urine. The leading factors of lithogenesis include: lithogenic ion concentration in the urine, lack of crystallization and aggregation inhibitors, the presence of stone-forming factors in the urine, and local changes in the kidneys.

The annual growth trend in the number of patients with urolithiasis from 2016 to 2020 was 23%. A significant factor in this growth is the late diagnosis of the disease, as well as the lack of some early diagnostic methods, in particular, scintigraphy and infrared spectrometry. The lack of an important diagnostic method for analyzing the composition of urinary stones, infrared spectrometry, and first-line non-invasive treatment methods, in particular, extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy, allows patients with urolithiasis to be referred for examination and treatment or surgical treatment outside the city. The availability of this equipment almost completely eliminates the need for surgical treatment [2].

Urinary tract infection is a common infectious disease, which is mainly treated in hospital. The effectiveness and speed of recovery depend on the correct choice of antibacterial drugs for the treatment of urinary tract infections. The choice of antibacterial therapy for urinary tract infections should be determined by the pathogen. Since treatment should be started before the results of urine culture are known, empirical broad-spectrum antibiotics are used in the treatment of urinary tract infections. However, this leads to a very rapid increase in the resistance of microbes to antibiotic therapy. To reduce this effect and increase the effectiveness of treatment, it is necessary to accurately predict the

suspected pathogen and prescribe the most appropriate antibiotic. In the clinical situation of urinary tract infection, it is possible to identify the likely pathogen, which will guide the choice of antibiotic therapy. This review proposes different therapeutic strategies for the treatment of urinary tract infections depending on the suspected pathogen, the clinical situation, and the characteristics of the patient.

Prescribing antibiotics for urinary tract infections is widespread. In fact, in 1997, it was estimated that up to 7 million visits to doctors in the United States were related to urinary tract infections. Information on the epidemiology of urinary tract infections is limited, as such patients often neglect to seek medical help and prefer self-medication. Also, urinary tract infections remain undiagnosed by doctors due to the uncertainty of the clinical presentation and non-specific symptoms of dysuria, which is often present in patients at risk of developing urinary tract infections [7].

Retrospective analysis of outpatient records of patients with urolithiasis who sought examination and specialized medical care at the outpatient department of the N.A. Lopatkin Research Institute of Urology. A retrospective analysis of 1,355 outpatient records of patients with urolithiasis treated for one year was conducted. According to the results, a tendency towards a female predominance was identified among adult patients with urolithiasis. Urolithiasis is more common in patients of working age, both men and women. The highest prevalence of patients of working age compared to patients who are not able to work is observed in male patients, more than three times. The largest number of outpatient visits for urolithiasis occurs in spring and autumn: in April and November. 75.2% of patients with urolithiasis have additional diseases such as dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes, and metabolic syndrome. Purine metabolism disorders can be observed not only in patients with uric acid urolithiasis,

but also in patients with calcium urolithiasis and magnesium ammonium phosphate stones.

The overall efficacy of Blemaren in the treatment of patients with hyperuricosuria and uric acid crystaluria, in the prevention of uric acid and calcium oxalate urolithiasis, and in the litholysis of uric acid stones in the absence of infectious or inflammatory processes is 96.9%. The side effect of dyspepsia was noted in less than 3% of patients [4].

Urolithiasis is one of the most common urological diseases. It occurs in all age groups, including children. According to various researchers, urolithiasis occurs in 1-5% of the population in industrialized countries. Bone changes develop only in the most severe, persistent cases of nephrolithiasis. Therefore, the treatment of metabolic bone damage associated with nephrolithiasis is directly related to the metaphylaxis of nephrolithiasis. More precisely, the treatment of skeletal complications is part of metaphylaxis. Drugs used to prevent recurrent stone formation can also be used to treat skeletal complications in some cases. On the contrary, drugs originally developed for the treatment of metabolic osteopathies may reduce the risk of recurrent nephrolithiasis. Theoretical coverage of the treatment of various forms of nephrolithiasis has been provided, but the specifics of drug treatment of patients with recurrent nephrolithiasis and skeletal damage remain relatively scarce.

Drug treatment of patients with renal osteodystrophy associated with nephrolithiasis is still poorly studied. In this clinical situation, it is difficult to even choose a pharmacological group or a specific drug. This is mainly due to the lack of comparative studies [6].

Analysis of the dynamics of changes in the immune status of patients with urinary tract infections is characterized by the transition of acute inflammatory reactions to subacute and chronic reactions, based on the deterioration of phagocytic function and increased indicators of secondary immunodeficiency. This leads to the formation of organ-specific autoallergies, which create a morphological basis for long-term inflammation and damage and should be taken into account in diagnosis and treatment.

Urinary tract infections are the most common type of infection affecting the human body. According to statistics, urinary tract infections are the second most common reason for outpatient treatment after respiratory tract infections. According to the American Urological Association, approximately 7 million patients in the United States visit doctors each year due to urinary tract infections, more than 100,000 patients are hospitalized, and the annual costs associated with this disease exceed \$1.6 billion.

The need to distinguish between complicated and uncomplicated urinary tract infections is determined by the differences in their etiology and treatment methods. It should be noted that uncomplicated urinary tract infections can manifest not only with mild and moderate symptoms, but also in severe forms with pronounced signs of intoxication [5].

Urolithiasis, or urinary stone disease, is a widespread condition globally, characterized by a high risk of recurrence and a significant impact on both

healthcare systems and the economy. According to research, the lifetime prevalence of this disease among the population of the United States averages 10.1%. In Saudi Arabia, however, the prevalence rate is notably higher, ranging from 13% to 19%. The primary factors influencing the development of the disease include insufficient fluid intake, hereditary predisposition, and dietary habits. Established risk factors consist of low fluid consumption, genetic susceptibility, and nutritional patterns.

A retrospective cohort study was conducted between 2020 and 2025 involving patients aged 18 years and older who had been diagnosed with urolithiasis. After excluding cases with incomplete data, a total of 353 patients were included in the final analysis. Factors such as age, sex, body mass index, and glomerular filtration rate were taken into account. According to the study results, patients who received vitamin D supplementation—particularly at higher doses—showed an increased likelihood of urolithiasis recurrence. This finding indicates the need to determine vitamin D dosage based on individual patient characteristics. Furthermore, the data emphasize the importance of conducting additional prospective studies to identify safe dosage thresholds for patients predisposed to stone formation.[1]

According to the World Health Organization, the prevalence of kidney stones in men and women in 2017–2018 was 11.9% and 9.4%, respectively. Over the past decade, the gender gap in the prevalence of kidney stones has been decreasing, and this trend is especially noticeable among women under 60 years of age. Retrospective studies aimed to study gender differences and the risk of developing chronic kidney disease among patients with kidney stones. According to the results of the study, the probability of developing chronic kidney disease is different between male and female patients, and the gender factor plays an important role in assessing the individual risk of patients. Data on patients diagnosed with kidney stones between 2013 and 2018 were retrospectively analyzed and divided into two groups according to gender. The study examined the clinical and demographic characteristics of the patients, the location and composition of the stones, the chemical parameters of urine and renal function. The study included 1,802 patients, with a higher proportion of male patients (1,312 men and 490 women). Hypertension, diabetes mellitus and dyslipidemia were more common in women, while calcium-containing stones, in particular calcium oxalate, uric acid and struvite stones, were dominant in men. Carbonate apatite stones were more common in women. Advanced surgical techniques and percutaneous nephrolithotomy and ureterorenoscopic lithotripsy were used more often in women than in men. The results of multivariate analysis showed that patients older than 60 years, female gender, uric acid stones, hypertension and diabetes were significant independent risk factors for the development of chronic kidney disease [3].

Study Objective. The objective of the study was to conduct a retrospective analysis of the medical records of hospitalized patients with urolithiasis and to

perform a pharmacoeconomic frequency analysis of the medications used in their treatment.

Research Methods. The study utilized the medical charts of hospitalized patients diagnosed with urolithiasis at the Polyclinic of the Republican Specialized Scientific-Practical Medical Center of Urology. A total of 1,802 surgical procedures were included in the retrospective analysis, of which 702 were performed on female patients and 1,100 on male patients. The research applied methods such as retrospective analysis, comparison, grouping, statistical evaluation, and pharmacoeconomic frequency analysis. Among pharmacoeconomic assessment techniques, quantitative frequency analysis was used to determine, based on evidence, whether specific medications were prescribed or not.

Results and Discussion. A total of 1,802 percutaneous surgical procedures were performed, including

702 procedures in female patients and 1,100 in male patients. Among these, surgeries conducted for the diagnoses “nephrolithotripsy for staghorn and multiple stones,” “nephrolithotripsy for a single stone,” and “nephrolithoextraction” accounted for 70.7% of all operations. Specifically, these procedures were performed in 516 women (representing 73.5% of all surgeries conducted in women) and in 758 men (representing 64.9% of all surgeries conducted in men). Furthermore, nephrolithotripsy for a single stone was performed in 485 patients, including 215 women and 270 men. Nephrolithotripsy for wheat-horn-type and multiple stones was performed in 457 patients, including 160 women and 297 men. Nephrolithoextraction was carried out in 332 patients, including 141 women and 191 men.

$$\text{Percentage of female patients} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of female patients}}{\text{Total number of patients}} \right) \times 100 = \frac{1117}{1838} \times 100 = 60,8$$

$$\text{Percentage of male patients} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of male patients}}{\text{Total number of patients}} \right) \times 100 = \frac{721}{1838} \times 100 = 39,2$$

Figure 1. Grouping of patients by age

In this type of surgery, the number of patients under the age of 20 is 40, 2.2% of the total number of patients, 595 from 21 to 40 - 33.0%, 775 from 41 to 60 - 43.0%, 392 from 61 to 80 - made up 21.8%.

$$\text{Age group percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of patients in the age group}}{\text{Total number of patients}} \right) \times 100$$

- Percentage of the 0–20 age group = $(76 / 1838) \times 100 = 4.1\%$
- Percentage of the 21–40 age group = $(595 / 1838) \times 100 = 32.4\%$
- Percentage of the 41–60 age group = $(775 / 1838) \times 100 = 42.2\%$
- Percentage of the 61–80 age group = $(385 / 1838) \times 100 = 20.9\%$
- Percentage of the 81–100 age group = $(7 / 1838) \times 100 = 0.4\%$

Figure 2. Age group indicators of patients

In the distribution of treated patients by region, those from Tashkent region and Tashkent city made up the main part. Of these, 518 people came from Tashkent city and 558 from Tashkent region.

Within the framework of the study, based on the diagnoses of a total of 1,838 patients, a total of 45,627 times of drug use were recorded according to pharmaco-economic frequency. Among the most commonly used drug dosage forms, the drug “Sodium chloride solution – 0.9%, 500.0 (M)” occupied a special place, which was used 2,478 times. It was also observed that “Sodium chloride solution – 0.9%, 5 ml, No. 10 (M)”

was used – 2,007 times, “Diclofenac sodium 2.5%, 3 X 10” – 1,443 times, “Extref vial, 2 g (M)” – 1,292 times.

In addition, according to the research results, “Furasemide 1%, 2 X 10 (M)” - 1,170 times, “Ceftazidime 1 g (M)” - 786 times, “Dimedrol 1%, 1 X 10 (M)” - 678 times, “Analgin solution 50%, 2 ml, No. 5 (M)” - 655 times, “Diclofenac suppository” 100 mg, No. 10 (M)” - 486 times, and “Novocaine solution 0.5%, 5 X 10 (M)” - 470 times. The data, studied within the disease treatment protocols, show a high demand for certain drugs, confirming their importance in practice and priority in clinical processes.

Table 1

Pharmaco-economic Frequency Analysis of Medications Used in the Treatment of Urolithiasis

No.	International Nonproprietary Name (INN)	Dosage Form	Drug Dosage	Frequency of Use	Total Usage Count
1	Sodium chloride solution	Solution for infusion	0.9% / 500 ml	2478	2 478
2	Sodium chloride solution	Solution for infusion	0.9% / 5 ml	2007	2 007
3	Diclofenac sodium	Solution for injection	2.5% / 3 ml	1 443	1 929
4		Rectal suppositories	10 mg / 10	486	
5	Extref	Powder for preparation of injection solution	2 mg per vial	1 292	1 292
6	Furosemide	Concentrate for preparation of infusion	1% / 2 ml	1 170	1 170
7	Ceftazidime	Powder for preparation of injection;	1 mg per vial	786	786
8	Diphenhydramine	Solution for infusion	1% / 1 ml	678	678
9	Analgin (Metamizole sodium)	Solution for injection	1% / 1 ml	655	655
10	Novocaine	Solution for injection	50% / 2 ml	470	470

Diclofenac sodium 2.5%, 3 X 10 was found to be used in approximately 70% of the patients studied in the study. The analysis shows that the number of use of this medicinal product mostly did not exceed 4 times.

In particular, this drug was used up to 4 times in patients treated with the diagnoses "C 67 right kidney formation, cT1bN0M0, RENAL 11H/ SPO - organ with pathology; percutaneous nephrolithotomy; left and "N 20.0 ICD (C67 - Malignant tumor of the urinary bladder according to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10); Stones in the right kidney; Hydronephrosis on the right side; Body mass index; ASA III; Anesthesiological risk level III; At the same time, "N 20.0 ICD; Stones in the renal pelvis of the right kidney; Hydronephrosis on the right side; Body mass index" ASA III" and "N 20.1 STK; Stones in the right back; Hydronephrosis on the right side; Body mass index" ASA III" In patients treated with diagnoses such as nephrostomy; Urinary tract infection; Anesthesia risk level II (ASA II), this drug was usually used up to 3 times. 23% of patients who used this drug used up to 2 times, and the remaining 87% used it once. This distribution indicates that "Diclofenac sodium" is actively used mainly as an adjuvant therapy to reduce pain and control inflammation. It also means that the frequency and dosage of the drug are determined depending on the clinical condition of the patient, the severity of the disease and individual characteristics.

The use of the drug "Extref vial, 2 g (M)" was relatively limited, and it was found that it was used mainly

in patients with severe clinical conditions. The analysis shows that this drug was used up to 4 times during the treatment of only three patients with the following diagnoses.

N20.1 N2 (ICD code). Fragmented stones located in the upper and lower one-third of the left ureter; left-sided ureteral hydronephrosis; urinary tract infection; acute complicated pyelonephritis on the left side. N20.1 (ICD code) – Stone in the upper one-third of the right ureter; right ureteral hypertrophy; urinary tract infection; acute complicated pyelonephritis on the right side; newly diagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus; stone in the lower one-third of the left ureter; left ureteral hypertrophy; body mass index; acute complicated pyelonephritis on the left side; stone at the lower end of the left ureter; left-sided hydronephrosis; body mass index; repeated episodes of acute complicated pyelonephritis on the left side.

In the remaining cases, the frequency of use of the drug was relatively low, with only 3% of the total number of patients taking it up to 3 times. At the same time, 44% of patients used the drug 2 times, and the remaining 52% used it only 1 time. Statistical data indicate that the drug "Extref Flakon" is used mainly as an adjuvant therapy in cases of severe complicated pyelonephritis, ureterohydronephrosis, accompanied by a high degree of inflammation during the diagnosis process. It is noted that the differences in the frequency of dosing are associated with the clinical condition of the patient, the severity of the disease, and individual reactions.

Table 2

Number of users	Diclofenac sodium 2,5 %, 3 X 10		Extref vial 2 g 2 r (M)		Furosemide 1 %, 2 x 10 (M)		Ceftazidime 1 g vial		Diphenhydramine injection 1 %, 1 X 10 (M)	
	Number of patients	Proportion of patients who used (%)	Number of patients	Proportion of patients who used	Number of patients	Proportion of patients who used (%)	Number of patients	Proportion of patients who used (%)	Number of patients	Proportion of patients who used (%)
Once/QD	1106	87	446	52	886	86	245	49	641	97
Twice daily/BID	148	12	381	45	136	13	232	46	17	3
Three times daily/TID	11	1	24	3	4	0,4	21	4	1	0,2
Four times daily/QID	2	0,2	3	0,4	–	XX X	2	0,4	XXX	XXX
Five times daily	XX X	XX X	XXX	XXX	XX X	XX X	XX X	XX X	XXX	XXX
Six times daily	XX X	XX X	XXX	XXX	XX X	XX X	1	0,2	XXX	XXX
Total	1267	69	854	47	1026	56	501	27	659	36

The drug "Furasemide 1%, 2x10 (M)" was found to be used in the treatment of approximately 56% of the patients studied in the study. In particular, this drug was used in the treatment of "N20.0 ICD – Right kidney stones; Right kidney hydronephrosis; Body mass index; ASA III"; N20.0 ICD; Left kidney stones; Left hydronephrosis; Left renal colic; Hypoplastic right kidney CRF; "N20.0 ICD; Right renal calculus; Right-sided hydronephrosis" and "N20.2 ICD – Stones in the right renal pelvis and ureter; Right-sided hydronephrosis; Acute complicated pyelonephritis on the right side were observed. It was most often used in patients undergoing treatment with a diagnosis of severe inflammatory process in the body, and the drug was used up to 3 times in total. Also, the analysis shows that 272 of the patients participating in the study used the drug up to 2 times, and the remaining 886 patients used it only once.

The drug "Ceftazidime 1 g (M)" was used in the treatment of approximately 27% of the patients studied in the study. The drug was used more often in particularly severe clinical cases, and in one patient with the diagnosis "N 20.0 ICD. Right kidney stones; Right kidney hydronephrosis; Body mass index; ASA III" it was used up to 6 times.

Similarly, in patients treated with the diagnoses 'N20.0 ICD — stones in the right kidney; right-sided hydronephrosis; body mass index; ASA III' and 'N20.2 ICD — a stone in the upper one-third of the right ureter and multiple stones in the left renal pelvis; right-sided ureteral hydronephrosis; left-sided hydronephrosis,' the frequency of drug administration reached up to four times. In the remaining cases, the medication was administered up to three times in 21 patients, twice in 232 patients, and only once in 245 patients.

Such a distribution indicates that ceftazidime is primarily used as an active therapeutic agent in cases accompanied by severe infectious complications, with the aim of eliminating inflammation and controlling the infection.

Diphenhydramine 1%, 1 × 10 (M) was used in a total of 659 patients within the study cohort, accounting for approximately 36% of all patients. Although the medication was administered once in most cases, some patients received it more frequently.

In particular, in the patient diagnosed with 'N20.0 ICD — blood clots in the urinary bladder; non-functioning nephrostomy on the left side; missing stent on the left side; post-percutaneous nephrolithotomy condition on the left side,' the medication was administered up to three times. Additionally, it was administered up to two times in 17 patients, while in the remaining 641 patients it was administered only once.

These data indicate that diphenhydramine is primarily used as an adjunctive therapeutic agent to prevent allergic reactions and provide anti-inflammatory effects, while its dosing frequency is determined according to the patient's clinical condition.

Conclusion.

1. It has been established that the correct timing of surgical intervention to optimize drug therapy in the treatment of patients with urolithiasis plays an important role in reducing the risk of disease recurrence.

2. In terms of pharmaco-economic frequency in urolithiasis, the frequency of drug use in patients

treated with a diagnosis of left-sided hydronephrosis reached 4 times. In the remaining cases, the drug was used up to 3 times in 21 patients, up to 2 times in 232 patients, and only 1 time in 245 patients. It was found that Ceftazidime was used mainly as an active therapeutic agent in cases with severe infectious complications, to eliminate inflammation and control infection.

3. According to the pharmaco-economic frequency analysis of drugs used in the treatment of urolithiasis, it was proven that "Extref" vial, 2 g, "Furasemide" 1%, 2 x 10, "Ceftazidime" 1 g - according to medical evidence, are widely used in the treatment process and constitute the largest part of the costs.

References

1. Alzaben N., Mokhtar A., Altwijri F., Alawaji S., Almannie R., Binsaleh S., Althunayan A. Association Between Vitamin D Supplementation and Urolithiasis Recurrence Outcomes in Known Stone Formers: A Retrospective Cohort Study // With Dose-Response Analysis. *Cureus*. – 2025 Aug. 24. – № 17 (8). – P. 10–23. – P. 10. doi: 10.7759/cureus.90853.
2. Arapiev Kh.B., Evloev D.M., Gagieva D.A. Ретроспективный анализ заболеваемости мочекаменной болезнью в РИ // *Modern Medicine Through the Eyes of Young Scientists. Proceedings of the II International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students, Residents, and Young Scientists*. Magas, Russian Federation. May 20, 2021. Alef. – P. 162–168. – P. 163.
3. Chien Tsu-Ming., Lu Yen-Man., Li Ching-Chia., Wu Wen-Jeng., Chang Hsueh-WeiChou., Yii-Her. A retrospective study on sex difference in patients with urolithiasis: who is more vulnerable to chronic kidney disease? // *Biology of Sex Differences*. – 2021.06.07. – № 12. – P. 40. DOI: 10.1186/s13293-021-00382-3.
4. Konstantinova O.V., Shaderkina V.A. Эпидемиологическая оценка мочекаменной болезни в амбулаторной урологической практике // *Organization of Urological Care. Experimental and Clinical Urology*. Moscow, Russian Federation. No. 1. 2015. www.ecuro.ru – P. 11–14. – P. 11.
5. Rustamov U.M., Sadikova D.I. Ретроспективный анализ литературных данных об инфекции мочевого тракта // "Economics and Society". Institute of Management and Socio-Economic Development. www.iupr.ru – Saratov, Russian Federation. No. 12 (103). 1. 2022. – P. 867–870. – P. 868.
6. Yarovoy S.K., Moskaleva N.G., Maksudov R.R. Лекарственная терапия метаболических поражений костного скелета при мочекаменной болезни // *Nephrology. Experimental and Clinical Urology*. Moscow, Russian Federation. 2014. No. 2. – P. 88–93. – P. 89.
7. Zhuravleva M.V., Yarovoy S.K., Prokofyev A.B., Berdnikova N.G., Ponomarenko T.M., Rodionov B.A., Kameneva T.R., Lazareva N.B., Serebrova S.Yu., Sukhobrus I.V. Актуальные вопросы эмпирической антимикробной терапии инфекции мочевыводящих путей со стратификацией пациентов по риску антибиотикорезистентности // *Antibiotics and Chemotherapy*. Moscow, Russian Federation. 2017. Vol. 62, No. 9–10. – P. 34–39. – P. 35.